

Launched in 2012, ClearPath Lending mortgage professionals are experts in their field and many are ranked among the best nationally. Unlike many mortgage companies in California whose primary sales point is rates and high pressure sales, our team of mortgage professionals will help educate you on the best loan options for your individual lending needs and help customize a loan specific to your needs. As a consummate mortgage professional, each ClearPath Lending employee from the top down is a committed to providing the very best in customer service throughout the loan process from application to closing. The focus of Lone Star Financing is to promote a strong reputation of integrity, customer service and upfront mortgage lending to all borrowers. This simple recipe has propelled us to one of the fast-growing mortgage companies in California.

ClearPath Lending combines an unwavering commitment to service excellence and value added mortgage expertise with continual research, development and implementation of leading edge technology, best industry practices, and local/national intelligence to ensure that each and every loan is well researched and administered.

ClearPath Lending business model is founded on the belief that competitive bid tension is necessary to ensure that the final loan options selected solely by the borrower are competitive and attractive. The final financing commitment and loan agreement must fully satisfy the borrower's needs and expectations in terms of loan amount, recourse, interest rate, amortization, and flexibility.

Transaction speed is critical to a funding and allows the borrower to be in a position to fix rate when deemed appropriate. Your financing requirements are discreetly and professionally distributed to all of our lender relationships that we have identified as most appropriate to finance your property. Our lending sources comprise a wide array of institutional and private mortgage investors, located across the U.S.